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The Global Innovation Index

It decreased by an average of -15.82% between 2013 and 2022 for the countries considered

The Global Innovation Index (GII) is an annual ranking that evaluates and measures the innovation performance of countries worldwide. It assesses the capabilities and results of innovation across different economies, considering both developed and emerging nations. The GII framework consists of approximately 80 indicators grouped into several key categories: institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, business sophistication, knowledge and technology outputs, and creative outputs. These categories encompass a wide range of factors, including political environment, education and research, technological infrastructure, investment, and the output of creative industries. The GII aims to capture the multi-dimensional facets of innovation, from the quality of education systems and the availability of high-tech services to the impact of innovation on the economy. The index is designed to provide policymakers, business leaders, and other stakeholders with comprehensive insights into how well different countries are fostering innovation. It highlights strengths and areas for improvement, encouraging policies that support the innovation ecosystem. By benchmarking global innovation capabilities, the GII serves as a tool for countries to monitor their progress and strategize on enhancing their innovation potential, ultimately driving economic growth and development.

The Global Innovation Index in 2022. The Global Innovation Index (GII) is a crucial measure of the innovative capabilities and achievements in various countries, reflecting their economic and political environments. The GII evaluates countries based on their ability to innovate, considering factors such as institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication. In the 2022 GII report, Switzerland leads the index with a score of 64.6, closely followed by the United States and Sweden. Switzerland (64.6) occupies the first place, unsurprisingly due to its strong institutions, robust business environment, and significant investments in research and development. The country also benefits from a highly skilled workforce and strong ties between academia and industry. The United States (61.8) ranks second, thanks to its large market size, high levels of venture capital, and strong collaboration between universities and industry. The presence of leading technology companies and a dynamic entrepreneurial ecosystem significantly contribute to this result. Sweden (61.6) follows closely, supported by excellent infrastructure quality, strong government support for innovation, and a high-level education system producing exceptional talents. The United Kingdom (59.7) and the Netherlands (58) complete the top five, both with advanced economies, excellent infrastructure, and a favorable startup environment. These countries have developed innovative ecosystems through favorable policies and high R&D spending. South Korea (57.8) stands out for its advanced technology sector and substantial research and development spending, making it a leader in technological innovation. Singapore (57.3) and Germany (57.2) are other prominent players, with Singapore benefiting from a stable and pro-business political environment, while Germany relies on its long tradition of engineering and innovative excellence. Finland (56.9) and Denmark (55.9) also show strong innovative capabilities, supported by high-level education systems and a rooted culture of innovation. China (55.3), although less advanced than the most innovative Western countries, has made enormous strides through significant R&D investments

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and government policies aimed at technological innovation. France (55) and Japan (53.6) maintain strong positions thanks to robust infrastructure, solid education systems, and a long tradition of innovation and scientific research. Hong Kong SAR, China (51.8), Canada (50.8), Austria (50.2), Estonia (50.2), and Israel (50.2) represent countries with very favorable environments for innovation, supported by strong government policies, investments in human capital, and advanced technological infrastructure. Luxembourg (49.8), Iceland (49.5), Malta (49.1), and Norway (48.8) are small countries that have managed to create innovative environments through targeted policies and strong support for new technologies. Ireland (48.5), New Zealand (47.2), Australia (47.1), and Belgium (46.9) also show considerable innovative potential, benefiting from open economies, strong education systems, and increasing attraction of foreign investments. Cyprus (46.2), Italy (46.1), Spain (44.6), the Czech Republic (42.8), the United Arab Emirates (42.1), and Portugal (42.1) represent economies significantly investing in innovation to improve their global competitiveness. Countries like Slovenia (40.6), Hungary (39.8), Bulgaria (39.5), Malaysia (38.7), Turkey (38.1), and Poland (37.5) show significant progress in the field of innovation, with policies favoring research and development and increasing private sector involvement. India (36.6) and Latvia (36.5) are emerging as new innovation hubs, with a strong focus on technological development and education. Countries with lower scores, such as Pakistan (23), Kenya (22.8), the Dominican Republic (22.7), Egypt (22.7), and many others, face significant challenges in terms of infrastructure, human capital, and institutions that limit their innovative potential. The bottom ranks of the index, occupied by countries like Niger (14.6), Mali (14.2), Angola (13.9), Yemen (13.8), and Mauritania (12.4), reflect severe deficiencies in institutional capacities, R&D investments, and technological infrastructure. In summary, the 2022 Global Innovation Index shows a varied landscape, with leading countries continuing to invest heavily in innovation, while many developing countries strive to close the gap with targeted policies and strategic investments. The ability to innovate is increasingly recognized as a key factor for sustainable economic growth and global competitiveness.

Global Innovation Index between 2013 and 2022. An analysis of the Global Innovation Index (GII) data between 2013 and 2022 reveals significant changes in the scores of various countries, highlighting trends of growth or decline in their capacity to innovate. China, with an increase from 44.7 to 55.3, saw an absolute increase of 10.6 points, equivalent to a percentage growth of 23.71%. This notable improvement reflects massive investments in research and development, as well as favorable government policies for innovation. Similarly, Iran improved its score from 27.3 to 32.9, an absolute increase of 5.6 points and a growth of 20.51%, suggesting significant progress despite economic and political challenges. South Korea saw an increase from 53.3 to 57.8, with an increase of 4.5 points, equivalent to 8.44%, confirming its position as a leader in technological and industrial innovation. Uzbekistan and Turkey showed more modest improvements of 5.86% and 5.83%, respectively, indicating stable but significant progress in their innovative capabilities. France, Japan, and Germany recorded slight increases in their GII scores, respectively by 4.17%, 2.68%, and 2.51%, indicating sustained but less dynamic growth compared to emerging countries like China. The United States, with an increase of 1.5 points (2.49%), maintains a strong position, but its growth rate is more contained compared to Asian competitors. India saw a minimal increase from 36.2 to 36.6, equivalent to 1.10%, suggesting the need for further efforts to improve its innovation environment. The United Arab Emirates and Sweden showed minimal variations, respectively 0.48% and 0.33%, suggesting stability in their already high levels of innovation. On the other hand, several countries recorded declines in their GII scores. Estonia, Pakistan, Vietnam, and the Philippines saw slight decreases, suggesting persistent challenges in maintaining their innovative competitiveness. The United Kingdom and Switzerland, traditionally strong in innovation, recorded decreases of 2.45% and 3.00%, respectively, indicating potential areas of stagnation. Austria, Singapore, Italy, and Denmark all showed significant declines in their scores, with decreases ranging from 3.28% to 4.12%. These declines can be attributed to various factors, including changes in government policies, economic fluctuations, or reductions in R&D investments. Countries like Bulgaria, Finland, the Netherlands,

Malta, and Cyprus recorded decreases in their scores ranging from 4.36% to 6.29%, suggesting a loss of momentum in their innovative capabilities. These declines potentially reflect a combination of internal and external factors that negatively affected their competitiveness. Morocco, Thailand, the Russian Federation, and Greece showed significant decreases, with negative percentage changes ranging from 6.80% to 8.49%. These declines highlight the difficulties these countries face in maintaining innovation levels in a competitive global context. Mauritius, Lithuania, Spain, and Israel recorded even more marked declines, with negative variations between 9.47% and 10.36%. In particular, Israel's decline, a country known for its strong startup culture and technological innovation, raises questions about potential changes in internal dynamics or government strategies. Countries like Brazil, Belgium, Australia, the Czech Republic, and Canada experienced significant declines, with variations ranging from 10.47% to 11.81%. These declines could reflect a combination of economic challenges, reductions in innovation investments, or changes in support policies. Luxembourg, Norway, Iceland, and Hong Kong SAR, China, recorded considerable declines in their scores, with negative variations ranging from 12.01% to 12.79%. These countries, although historically strong in innovation, may have faced specific challenges that negatively affected their innovative capabilities. New Zealand, Ukraine, Slovenia, and Serbia showed significant declines in their GII scores, with negative percentage changes ranging from 13.39% to 14.78%. These declines suggest the need for strategic interventions to reverse the trend and stimulate innovation. Countries like Croatia, Hungary, Romania, Mexico, and Jamaica experienced marked declines, with variations ranging from 15.04% to 15.81%. These declines indicate persistent difficulties in maintaining or improving the infrastructure and policies supporting innovation. Ireland, Chile, Malaysia, and the Slovak Republic recorded even more significant declines, with negative variations between 16.23% and 18.72%. These countries may have faced economic and political challenges that limited their ability to innovate. Countries like Madagascar, Saudi Arabia, Peru, and Panama showed marked declines in their GII scores, with negative percentage changes ranging from 18.78% to 19.18%. These declines suggest structural difficulties in continuously supporting innovation. Latvia, Oman, Bangladesh, Qatar, Egypt, and Sri Lanka recorded significant declines, with variations ranging from 19.25% to 20.39%. These declines indicate that, despite past progress, there are substantial challenges these countries must face to improve their innovative capabilities. Countries like Belarus, South Africa, Albania, and Bosnia and Herzegovina experienced marked declines in their GII scores, with negative percentage changes ranging from 20.52% to 21.27%. These declines likely reflect a combination of economic, social, and political challenges that have hindered innovation. Georgia, Mongolia, the Kyrgyz Republic, Colombia, and Tunisia recorded significant declines, with variations ranging from 21.63% to 22.07%. These countries face significant challenges to reverse this negative trend and improve their innovative capabilities. Countries like Bahrain, Botswana, Uruguay, Côte d'Ivoire, and Moldova experienced marked declines in their GII scores, with negative percentage changes ranging from 22.71% to 23.96%. These declines suggest the need for strategic interventions to improve policies and investments in innovation. Argentina, Kazakhstan, Zimbabwe, North Macedonia, and Kenya recorded significant declines, with variations ranging from 24.14% to 24.75%. These countries face structural challenges that limit their ability to innovate and compete globally. Countries like Paraguay, Montenegro, Azerbaijan, Tanzania, and Jordan experienced marked declines in their GII scores, with negative percentage changes ranging from 25.41% to 26.54%. These declines indicate persistent difficulties in sustaining innovation and improving competitiveness. Kuwait, Cambodia, Namibia, Algeria, and Yemen recorded significant declines, with variations ranging from 27.00% to 28.50%. These countries face substantial challenges to reverse this negative trend and improve their innovative capabilities. Armenia, Nepal, Costa Rica, the Dominican Republic, and Ghana experienced marked declines in their GII scores, with negative percentage changes ranging from 29.26% to 32.03%. These declines likely reflect a combination of economic, social, and political challenges that have hindered innovation. Rwanda, Nicaragua, Ethiopia, Togo, and Senegal recorded significant declines, with variations ranging from 32.25% to 34.75%. These countries face significant challenges to reverse this negative trend and improve their innovative capabilities. El Salvador, Nigeria, Tajikistan, Brunei

Darussalam, and Ecuador experienced marked declines in their GII scores, with negative percentage changes ranging from 36.42% to 38.11%. These declines indicate persistent difficulties in sustaining innovation and improving competitiveness. Niger, Honduras, Trinidad and Tobago, Angola, and Zambia recorded significant declines, with variations ranging from 39.17% to 41.04%. These countries face structural challenges that limit their ability to innovate and compete globally. Countries like Cameroon, Benin, Burkina Faso, Mozambique, and Guatemala experienced marked declines in their GII scores, with negative percentage changes ranging from 41.25% to 43.49%. These declines suggest the need for strategic interventions to improve policies and investments in innovation. Uganda and Mali recorded the most significant declines, respectively 49.68% and 50.69%, indicating enormous challenges in sustaining innovation. These countries face substantial structural, economic, and political difficulties to improve their innovative capabilities and compete globally. In conclusion, the analysis of GII data from 2013 to 2022 shows a clear disparity between countries that have improved their innovative capabilities and those that have experienced a decline. While some emerging countries like China have made remarkable progress, many others, including some traditionally strong in innovation, have seen a decline in their innovative capabilities. Economic, political, and structural challenges play a crucial role in these dynamics, highlighting the need for targeted policies and strategic investments to support and enhance innovation globally.

Economic Policies for the Development of the Global Innovation Index. To increase the Global Innovation Index (GII) globally, it is essential to implement a series of targeted economic policies that encourage sustainable and inclusive innovation. First, it is crucial to increase investments in research and development (R&D) from both the public and private sectors. Governments and businesses must collaborate to fund innovative projects, create tax incentives for companies investing in R&D, and establish partnerships between universities and industries to promote applied research. Another fundamental strategy is to improve the quality of education at all levels, with a particular emphasis on STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics). Training a skilled workforce is essential to support an innovative ecosystem; this also includes promoting continuous learning and reskilling to adapt to technological changes. Additionally, immigration policies must be oriented to attract global talents. Offering facilitated visas and residence permits for researchers, engineers, and entrepreneurs can enrich a country's pool of skills and innovative ideas. At the same time, it is crucial to improve digital infrastructure, ensuring access to fast and affordable internet, and investing in emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, and the Internet of Things (IoT). These investments facilitate the adoption of new technologies by businesses and stimulate innovation. Another key aspect is creating a regulatory environment favorable to innovation. Regulations must be agile and adaptable, supporting new business models and disruptive technologies without stifling creativity with excessive bureaucracy. Promoting intellectual property (IP) is equally important: a robust IP system ensures that innovators can protect and monetize their ideas, further incentivizing creativity. In parallel, fair competition must be guaranteed to avoid monopolies that could stifle innovation; effective antitrust policies are therefore essential. Economic policies should also incentivize the creation and development of innovative startups and SMEs. This can be done through facilitated access to funding, venture capital, and acceleration programs. Startups often drive innovation but need support to overcome initial barriers and scale quickly. Furthermore, it is important to promote a culture of innovation through educational programs, networking events, and collaboration platforms that encourage idea exchange and experimentation. Sustainability must be integrated into innovation policies. Investing in green technologies and promoting the adoption of sustainable practices not only addresses environmental challenges but also creates new business opportunities. Economic policies should incentivize research and innovation in sectors such as renewable energy, energy efficiency, sustainable agriculture, and waste management. Another crucial element is promoting digital inclusion. It is essential to ensure that all segments of the population have access to the technologies and skills necessary to participate in the digital economy. This requires investments in infrastructure in rural and disadvantaged areas, as well as training programs

to bridge the digital divide. International cooperation plays a fundamental role in increasing the GII. Sharing best practices, cooperation in transnational research projects, and support for global initiatives can accelerate technological progress. International organizations, governments, and businesses must collaborate to address global challenges such as climate change, public health, and food security through innovation. Fiscal policies must be oriented to support innovation. Tax cuts, R&D activity tax credits, and incentives for investments in advanced technologies can stimulate innovative activity. However, it is important that these policies are transparent and accessible to all businesses, regardless of their size. Promoting diversity and inclusion in the innovation sector is another crucial aspect. Policies must ensure that women, minorities, and other underrepresented groups have equal opportunities to contribute to innovation. This can be achieved through mentorship programs, incentives for diversified hiring, and initiatives promoting gender equality in STEM. Another central point is data protection and cybersecurity. While digital technologies offer immense opportunities, they also increase the risks of cyberattacks and privacy violations. Robust cybersecurity and data protection policies are essential to build trust in the digital system and promote the adoption of new technologies. Economic policies must also address the entry barriers for new innovative enterprises. Reducing bureaucracy, simplifying business registration processes, and providing legal and administrative support can facilitate the creation of new businesses and accelerate their development. Finally, it is crucial to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of innovation policies. Establishing clear indicators and feedback systems allows for the rapid adaptation of policies to emerging needs and ensures that investments produce the desired results. Transparency and accountability are essential to maintain public and investor trust in innovation initiatives. In summary, increasing the Global Innovation Index globally requires an integrated approach that combines investments in R&D, improving education, favorable immigration policies, advanced digital infrastructure, agile regulations, promoting intellectual property, supporting startups, sustainability, digital inclusion, international cooperation, fiscal incentives, diversity and inclusion, data protection, reducing entry barriers, and constant policy monitoring. Only through a coordinated and multifaceted commitment is it possible to create a global environment that fosters innovation and allows for addressing future challenges with creativity and resilience.

Conclusions. The average value of the Global Innovation Index decreased between 2013 and 2022 by -15.82%, going from 38.5 units to 32.4 units. Some countries have significantly increased their Global Innovation Index levels far beyond the average value, such as China with +23.71%, Iran with +20.51%, South Korea with +8.44%, Uzbekistan with +5.86%, and Turkey with +5.83%. There are also regions where the value of the Global Innovation Index has decreased, such as Mozambique with -43.40%, Guatemala with -43.39%, Uganda with -49.68%, and Mali with -50.69%. In general, the average value of the Global Innovation Index for upper-middle-income countries tends to be above 40.00%.

Leogrande, A. (2024). *Cultural and Creative Employment Across Italian Regions* (No. hal-04528709).

Leogrande, A. (2024). *Knowledge Workers across the Italian Regions* (No. 4bv6a). Center for Open Science.

Leogrande, A. (2024). *The Propensity for Patenting in the Italian Regions* (No. 120553). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A. (2024). *The Innovation of the Production System in the Italian Regions* (No. 120542). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A., Resta, E., & Costantiello, A. (2024). *The Renunciation of Healthcare Services in the Italian Regions in the ESG Context*. Available at SSRN 4746676.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). *The regulatory quality in the light of environmental, social and governance framework at world level*. *Discover Global Society*, 2(1), 1.

Resta, E., Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., & Leogrande, A. (2024). *The Impact of Patent Applications on Technological Innovation in European Countries*. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 28(3), 1-15.

Resta, E., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2024). *The Opportunity Driven Entrepreneurship in the Context of Innovation Systems in Europe in the Period 2010-2019*. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP*, 28(3), 1-13.

Resta, E., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2024). *The Impact of New Doctorate Graduates on Innovation Systems in Europe*. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 28(3), 1-22.

Magazzino, C. & Leogrande, A. (2024). *The Role of Air Pollution in the ESG Model at the World Level*. In C. Popescu & P. Yu (Eds.), *Intersecting Environmental Social Governance and AI for Business Sustainability* (pp. 93-122). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3693-1151-6.ch004>

Resta, E., Resta, O., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). *The hospital emigration to another region in the light of the environmental, social and governance model in Italy during the period 2004-2021*. *BMC Public Health*, 24(1), 1880.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). *The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy. A Data-Driven Analysis*. University Library of Munich, Germany.